

Survey on International Collaborations in Coral Reef Science

Project Description: The aim of our project is to gain in-depth knowledge of the dynamics of international collaborations among coral reef scientists/practitioners. Developed in collaboration with global coral reef scientists, this survey aims to capture valuable insights and experiences to better understand the mechanisms of international collaborations. By participating in this survey, you can contribute to building a clearer understanding of the underlying mechanisms of collaborations from researcher/practitioners' perspectives and help us develop actionable recommendations for enhancing collaboration in coral reef science.

Participation: It should take approximately 20 minutes to complete the survey. Please respond by end of December. Your responses will be kept strictly confidential, and all data will be de-identified to ensure your anonymity. Before agreeing to participate, please take the time to read this explanation outlining the conditions for participation. Feel free to ask any questions at coralreefcollab.survey@kaust.edu.sa

Voluntary participation and right to withdraw

Your participation in this research project is completely voluntary. You are free to refuse to participate and you may withdraw from this project at any time, without consequences or recrimination. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason. Should you choose to withdraw, please advise the research team by sending an email to Dr. Shannon Klein at coralreefcollab.survey@kaust.edu.sa. In case you withdraw from the study, all your non-anonymised data will be destroyed. If your data has already been analysed, the results will be used but the source of the data will not be retrievable.

Terms of participation

Data will be kept anonymous and secure for 5 years after the end of the study and will then be deleted. Results of this research study may be published in scientific journals; however, it won't be possible to identify you as an individual.

Compensation and indemnity

No monetary compensation will be provided. By participation, you will contribute to the development of recommendations and guidelines for research integrity in international collaborations. The study poses a small risk of discovering sensitive information, for instance about research misconduct cases or problems with how specific institutions deal with research integrity issues. We will take all steps necessary to minimise this risk by asking all

participants to not provide names of people/institutions in the survey, and by anonymising all data. We have secured ethical clearance from King Abdullah University of Science and Technology's (KAUST) Institutional Biosafety and Bioethics Committee (IBEC) under Protocol: 23IBEC062.

Data storage and use

All data collected through the online survey will be stored on the MS Forms and Datawaha. The access to the stored data will be enabled only for select project members from King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST) while other partners in the project

Consent

1. By clicking the button below, you acknowledge that:

- you are 18 years of age
- your participation in the study is completely voluntary
- you have taken the desired time to make a decision regarding your participation in this research
- you are aware that you may choose to terminate your participation in the study at any time and for any reason
- you are under no obligation to answer every question in this form

*

I consent, start survey!

Your Information

2. What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- I prefer not to answer
- Other

3. What is your Nationality:

4. In which country do you currently reside:

5. How many years of experience do you have working on coral reefs? *

- None, I don't work in this field
- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 5 years
- 6 to 10 years
- 11 to 20 years
- More than 20 years

6. In which countries are your coral reef science projects based in? (Type all that apply)

7. What best describes your work:

- Academia / University
- Industry (e.g consulting)
- Government
- NGO
- Other

8. If you selected academia, specify:

- Student (Bachelor, Master)
- PhD
- Post-doc
- Technician
- Early career researcher (< 5years)
- Senior researcher (>5 years)
- Professor/ Principal Investigator
- Other

9. Which 3 countries do you mostly collaborate with? (type out 3 countries)

10. How have you previously 'connected' with international collaborators?
(select all that apply)

- Conferences
- Searching publications
- Social media (twitter, instagram, linkedIn)
- Introduced by previous collaborators or associates
- Recommendations from government where you want to conduct fieldwork
- Searching Google
- Other

11. How do you make yourself visible and promote your research? (select all that apply)

- None
- Social media
- Website
- Blogs
- News
- Podcasts
- Press releases
- Scientific publications
- Other

12. If you selected "none", why do you not promote your research? (select all that apply)

- No time
- Lack of tools and know how
- Language barrier
- Not of value for me
- I don't want to
- Other

Collaboration experience

13. How many international research projects have you participated in during the course of your career?

- None
- 1-5
- 6-10
- 10 -20
- More than 20

14. How many publications resulting from international research projects have you contributed to during the course of your career?

- None
- 1-5
- 6-10
- 10 -20
- More than 20

15. In your experience, how would you describe the ratio of contacting other researchers for collaborations compared to being contacted by international researchers to collaborate?

- I primarily initiate contact for collaborations and am rarely contacted by others.
- I am contacted and initiate contact for collaborations with roughly equal frequency.
- I am mostly contacted by others for collaborations and rarely initiate contact.

16. What is the most common response you receive when you reach out to researchers internationally to engage in an international collaboration?

- No reply
- Request for further information
- Answered invitation but not interested
- Answered invitation but not available
- Positive reply resulting in collaboration
- Other

17. How do you generally respond to invitations to collaborate on international projects?

- No reply
- Request for further information
- Answered invitation but not interested
- Answered invitation but not available
- Positive reply resulting in collaboration
- Other

18. Provide a motivation for your response above:

In other words why do you respond to invitations in this way?

19. How often are your international collaborations reoccurring?

In other words, how often do you engage in collaborations with the same international partners on new projects?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

20. What role do you usually fulfill in international collaborations?

Select all that apply!

- Conceptualising and designing study
- Data collection
- Data analysis
- Writing
- Administrative and logistical support
- Providing resources
- Providing local knowledge
- Acquiring funding
- Other

21. How does your role in the previous question vary compared to a domestic/local collaboration?

- Less responsibility in local collaborations
- Same
- More responsibility in local collaborations

22. Please explain why

23. Do you feel like your knowledge and expertise are adequately recognized in international collaboration projects?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

24. When international researchers visit your region, how often do you believe they appropriately recognize the local expertise and knowledge?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

25. Do you feel like you are offered the opportunity to valuably contribute to different components of the research project?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

26. In recurring collaborations, how often does your role 'evolve' over time to reflect more responsibility?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

27. Have you encountered challenges related to divergent understandings of local practices, regulations, or expectations when collaborating internationally?

This could include situations where collaborators from one country might not be aware of the need for compensation, special permits, or other country-specific considerations in the collaboration process.

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

28. In your experience, has an international collaboration required you to work on your own time, without compensation, and/or at a personal cost?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

29. Have you experienced 'Tokenism' in your international collaborations?

Tokenism is the practice of making only a perfunctory or symbolic effort to be inclusive to members of minority groups, especially by recruiting people from underrepresented groups in order to give the appearance of racial or gender equality within a workplace or educational context.

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

30. When you enter international collaborations are there mechanisms in place for data management?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

31. If no mechanisms exist, how often is data shared in your international collaborative research projects?

Consider situations where international collaborators come to conduct a project with you, do you get access to all this data and vice versa?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

32. How would you rate the clarity regarding data ownership and data sharing in your collaborative projects?

- Extremely unclear
- Somewhat unclear
- Neither clear nor unclear
- Somewhat clear
- Extremely clear

33. Have you or your colleagues experienced 'parachute science' in your region of residence?

Parachute science is the practice whereby international scientists from higher-income countries, conduct field studies in a lower income nation, without engaging or acknowledging any local researchers.

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

34. What are the impacts of such practices in your experience?

Provide keypoints

Benefits of International Collaborations

35. In your experience, are international collaborations important for:

Note: Your region refers to your country of residence

	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	I don't know
Producing high-quality publications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge transfer and capacity building in your region	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Producing meaningful conservation and management recommendations in your region	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Acquiring funding	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Authorship experiences in international collaborations

36. Is authorship discussed in your international collaborative research projects?

Consider situations where international collaborators come to conduct fieldwork with you, do you discuss authorship and authorship contribution statements?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

37. Have there been instances where international collaborators had differing expectations about authorship and contributions?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

38. Do you think that authorship and contribution agreements in your international collaborations were generally fair and just?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

39. Have you ever been excluded or not adequately acknowledged for your authorship contribution(s)?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

40. Have you ever encountered disagreement regarding authorship naming?

This includes the ordering / position of authors on the article

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

41. If yes, have you taken action about it?

For instance raising a complaint or authorship dispute etc

- No
- Yes
- I don't know

42. If yes, how satisfied were you with the outcome?

- Not at all Satisfied
- Partly Satisfied
- Satisfied
- More than Satisfied
- Very Satisfied

43. If not satisfied, why?

44. If you didn't take any action, why?

Barriers to leading science

45. What type and level of support do you receive to lead projects from your institution, work place or similar?

Provide keywords with level of support in parenthesis!

Example: Funding (high), administrative support (low), dedicated hours for publication work (moderate), editing service (low) etc

46. What are your main impediments to lead research projects?

Examples include: Administration, procurement, access to field sites, funding etc

47. How important is publishing in international peer-reviewed journals for you?

Not at all important

Important

Very Important

I don't know

48. What percentage of your research gets published in international peer-reviewed journals?

The value must be a number

49. What do you estimate is the average percentage of work that local researchers publish in international peer-reviewed journals in your region?

Your region, refers to your country of residence.

The value must be a number

50. In your experience, do you believe that collaborating with international researchers enhances the likelihood of your work getting published in international peer-reviewed journals?

- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- I don't know

51. What are current barriers for you to publishing?

Select all that apply!

- Funding
- Time
- Infrastructure and resources
- Skills and expertise
- Language barrier
- Other

52. Do you use any AI tools to help with overcoming publishing barriers?

Examples include ChatGPT, Grammarly etc

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always

53. If you do not use AI, why?

54. Have you/your working group applied to international funding agencies?

- Yes
- No
- I am not aware of any I am eligible for
- I don't know

55. If you have applied to international funding, how often were you successful in receiving the funding?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half of the time
- Most of the time
- Always
- I don't know

56. If you have not applied to international funding, what are the main reasons?

- Lack of time
- Language barrier
- Too competitive
- Political reasons
- Other

57. Are you part of any international coral reef communities/networks?

Examples include: International coral reef initiative (ICRI), International coral reefs society (ICRS) etc

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

58. If yes, what level and what type of support do you receive from these?

Examples: discounted publication fees (moderate), covering travel costs (high) etc

Recommendations

59. Based on your experiences, what strategies or best practices do you recommend for fostering an equitable and inclusive research environment during international collaborations?

60. What role can funding agencies play in promoting equity and research integrity in international collaborations?

61. What provisions could funding agencies have in place to promote participation of scientists from developing nations?

62. What role can publishing agencies play in promoting equity and research integrity in international collaborations?

63. And what provisions could publishing agencies have in place to promote participation of scientists from developing nations?

Thank you so much for taking the time to respond to this survey!

If you are interested in further discussing recommendations and collaborate please contact us at:

coralreefcollab.survey@kaust.edu.sa

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